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1. Introduction

This report provides an overview of the use cases planned for the eRImote project and examines the challenges identified during expert group meetings and workshops. This report aligns these challenges with the current use cases to see where the use cases can begin pointing to solutions for the identified challenges as well as helping us identify areas not covered. In these areas **additional use cases are here proposed** which could, outside of the framework of the eRImote project, identify specific and generalisable solutions.

2. Pre-defined use cases

During the writing phase, the eRImote consortium has already identified some use cases (see **figure 1**) based on the experience of the project partners in remote access provision and already encountered challenges. These use cases cover different aspects of remote/digital access, including administrative components, Remote/digital access procedures, Data management, Training and workforce development.

Figure 1: Graphical illustration of the pre-defined use cases

3. Identified challenges

As part of the eRImote project activities especially within WP3: Remote access landscape analysis, we organized a series of expert group meetings across five different thematic areas: **Expert Group I** - Researcher experiences with remote/virtual access, sample handling and quality assurance, **Expert Group II** - Data sharing, Data access and security, **Expert Group III** - Remote training for RI staff and researchers, **Expert Group IV** - Remote Instrument control and **Expert Group V** - International access and accessibility of RI services. We have also conducted three workshops: **workshop 1** - Remote training for RI users and staff & User interactions and networking in remote/digital service provision, **workshop 2** - Remote operations of RI services and Data and access security, and **workshop 3** - Governance, Policy, Funding, and Impact. These different expert group meetings and workshops hosted more than **40 experts** and served as a platform for exchange among **more than 200** scientific, technical and industrial actors active in remote access provision which allowed us to extract valuable information.

These efforts enabled us to identify **15** distinct challenges related to the provision of remote access to research infrastructures across Europe (**see figure 2**).

Figure 2: Graphical illustration of identified challenges

To streamline our approach, we categorized these 15 challenges into six main categories: **Effort and expertise, logistical and regulatory challenges, training and skill development, cybersecurity and technical requirements, instrumentation and access, and networking and collaboration.**

This structured organization has been instrumental in addressing the complexities of remote access in a comprehensive and focused manner, ensuring that all identified issues are systematically tackled.

After analysing the data obtained from the different expert group meetings and workshops and cross-checking the newly identified challenges with the descriptions and expected outcomes of our predefined use cases, we were successful in identifying several compatibilities. This alignment means that most of the identified challenges are indeed covered by our current use cases (see figure 3).

Figure 3: Graphical illustration of alignment between the pre-defined use cases and newly identified challenges

4. New use cases

Nevertheless, our analysis also revealed that not every challenge could be matched to any current use cases. The latter indicates the necessity to formulate new use cases, which will fit exactly these unmatched challenges.

The main challenge categories so far critically unaddressed are:

- **Logistical and regulatory challenges**
- **Cybersecurity and technical requirements**

As well as some aspects of **Efforts and Expertise**. We want to recognise that not all challenges are equally suitable for addressing via use cases, such as regulatory issues or increase requirements of staff time, and some represent difficulties inherent to remote access for which there are no specific solutions, such as the reduced personal collaboration or hands-on training.

At the same time, many additional use cases can be imagined, both those addressing different aspects orthogonal to the already established use cases, as well as such that explore so far unaddressed challenges. We here propose as examples two new use cases which could be explored outside of the eRImote project framework. (aSee figure 4).

Figure 4: Graphical illustration of the new use cases

The implementation of such new use cases as **Comprehensive Cybersecurity Framework for Remote Research**, and **Optimized Logistics for Sample Shipment** will fill existing gaps in a big way to improve remote access to research infrastructures.

In this way, the **Comprehensive Cybersecurity Framework** will guarantee providing RIs staff and users with the necessary knowledge for safe and reliable remote operations, securing sensitive data. Finally, **Optimized Logistics for Sample Shipment** streamline both the regulatory and logistical processes, through which research samples are transported effectively and compliantly. These use cases will strengthen the robustness, security, and efficiency of remote access to research infrastructures.

It should be noted that these use cases are large scale efforts, much more significant in scope than the use cases implemented in the eRImote project. When considering their practical implementation, a split into sub-aspects or parallel projects in different domains should be considered for most impactful implementation.

Unrelated to the use cases above which are focussed on specific practical implementation of remote access in the RI landscape, the discussions in the eRImote-organised workshops and Expert Groups have also revealed two additional challenges in need of further in-depth exploration, for which case studies could be implemented. These are:

- 1) **Environmental impact of remote access** – Achieving a full and balanced estimation of the true environmental impact of remote access is complex. The insights from eRImote reveal that in addition to the overall intrinsic environmental benefits of RIs, and the environmental benefit of reduced travel related to remote access, a loss of efficiency in experimentation and the resulting wasted time and energy must be considered. Therefore, case studies that explore a global picture of the environmental impact of remote access could be implemented.
- 2) **Increased requirement of staff time and expertise** represents more of a policy, planning and budgeting challenge for the RIs and the exact requirements of increased time and expertise would initially have to be identified, to allow for suggestions on how this challenge can be specifically addressed.